

Short communication

First report of *Lepinotus reticulatus* and *Ectopsocus vishnyakovae* (Insecta: Psocoptera) from Iran

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چکیده

طی مطالعات انجام شده در اردیبهشت ۱۳۹۳ روی فون بندپایان درخت زبان گنجشک در شهرستان مشهد و حومه، نمونه‌هایی از شپش‌های چوب و کتاب جمع‌آوری گردید. نمونه‌ها نزد دکتر Charles Lienhard در موزه تاریخ طبیعی سوئیس ارسال گردید که با نام‌های *Ectopsocus vishnyakovae* Schmidt (Psocoptera) و *Lepinotus reticulatus* Enderlein (Psocoptera: Trogiidae) گزارش شناسایی شد. هر دو گونه برای فون ایران گزارش جدید محسوب می‌شوند.

In 2014, during the study of the arthropods of ash trees in Mashhad and its vicinity, some psocids were collected and sent to Dr Charles Lienhard (Swiss Museum of Natural History). The specimens were identified as *Ectopsocus vishnyakovae* Schmidt and *Lepinotus reticulatus* Enderlein, of the families Ectopsocidae and Trogiidae, respectively. Both species and the family Trogiidae are new to Iran.

The suborder Trogiomorpha contains about 340 species and seven families including the family Trogiidae. Members of this family are recognized by the following characters: head short and broad; maxillary palpus with conical sensillum on inner side of second segment; hind tibia and tarsus together shorter than abdomen; wings absent or weakly developed (small forewing rudiments are found in some genera); paraprocts with strong anal spine; lacking trichobothria (New, 1974). The genus *Lepinotus* Heyden has a worldwide distribution and includes 11 species (Lienhard & Smithers, 2002). The species *L. reticulatus* is parthenogenetic and is associated with birds and nests of mammals as well as soil and grain storehouses (Mockford, 1993).

Ectopsocus vishnyakovae belongs to the largest suborder Psocomorpha, which consists of 30 of the 45 extant families. Ectopsocidae is represented in the Neotropical region by 29 species in the three genera *Ectopsocus* McLachlan, *Ectopsocopsis* Badonnel and *Belipsocus* García Aldrete (Manchola *et al.*, 2014).

- *Lepinotus reticulatus* Enderlein

Material examined – Khorasan-e Razavi: 2 ♀♀, Mashhad, N 36°15', E 59°38', 30.xi.2014, leg. F. Khandehroo.

Diagnosis – Head pale reddish brown, without markings; vertex and frons broad, without epicranial arm; ocelli absent; forewing short, reddish brown with a distinct reticulate pattern and setae; hindwing absent (Feiyang *et al.*, 2012).

Distribution – This species has been recorded from Turkey, Caucasia, Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Lebanon, Syria, Israel, Jordan, Sinai Peninsula (Egypt), Arabian peninsula, Iraq as well as North Africa.

- *Ectopsocus vishnyakovae* Schmidt

Material examined – Khorasan-e Razavi: 1 ♀, Mashhad, N 36°15', E 59°38'; 7.x.2014, leg. F. Khandehroo.

Diagnosis – Female is characterised as follows: body length 1.7-2.0 mm; dark brown; forewing short (brachypterous form) or complete (macropterous form), tinged with brown; dorsal valvula of gonapophyses (v2) with pointed apex; subgenital plate distally bilobate, lobes elongate, basally broad, tapered, heavily sclerotized, with stout apical spine as well as setae on outer and inner sides. Male unknown.

Distribution – This species occurs in Armenia and Turkmenistan.

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